

Relevance of cross-section analysis in correct diagnosis of the state of conservation of building materials as evidenced by spectroscopic imaging

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Abstract

In the present work the need to use cross-section analysis as a routine procedure in order to characterise physiochemical damage on building materials was evaluated using a combination of spectroscopic imaging techniques based on Raman spectroscopy, XRF and SEM-EDX.

Firstly, samples for cross-section analysis required special preparation in order to avoid the loss of soluble and weakly anchored compounds and thereby ensure the representativeness of the analysis. To this end, samples were dry drilled and fractured with a single blow rather than cut, so as to avoid friction. Cross-section analysis allowed surface deposition (crusts and patinas) to be differentiated from penetrating pollution and the affected depth to be determined. Elemental and molecular distributions were obtained to establish the origin of the compounds/elements found. Moreover, establishing the depth reached by the pollutant, which depends on material porosity, can help to determine the physicochemical form of the pollutant. Finally, SEM-EDX images allowed surface and internal cracks, as well as the causes of these physical stresses, to be identified. As a result, surface analysis alone was shown to lead to incomplete or

even incorrect conclusions that can be avoided by using cross-section analysis as a routine procedure when assessing the state of conservation of building materials.

Keywords

Cross-section, drillings, building materials, spectroscopic imaging, penetration capacity

INTRODUCTION

The impact of acid gases on buildings materials has been widely studied because of their notable and visible consequences¹⁻³. Atmospheric contamination can seriously affect not only building façades but also structural integrity. Moreover, pollutants accumulate on the surface of the materials and therefore buildings could be considered pollutant repositories⁴⁻⁷. Recent studies in this field reveal that the accumulation is not only superficial, as pollutants can penetrate materials. Determining the extent of penetration is important to be able to assess the real state of conservation of building materials, in order to carry out restoration work in built heritage. However, this factor is not often studied.

For this purpose, cross-section analysis is widely used as a routine procedure in other fields of cultural heritage, especially in art, where examples of the use of cross-section in paintings and other artefacts abound⁸⁻¹⁶. Cross-section analysis provides, for example, the morphology and stratigraphy of paintings^{11, 13, 17, 17-19}.

Generally, the analytical techniques used to carry out the cross-section analysis are based on spectroscopic techniques. Among them, techniques based on elemental and vibrational spectroscopy such as X-Ray Fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF), X-Ray Diffraction spectroscopy (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopes with Energy-Dispersive X-Ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX), Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR)

spectroscopy, Laser-Induced Breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS) or Raman spectroscopy are some of the most typical^{9, 14, 15, 20-25}. There are two main advantages to these techniques. One is that they are non-destructive, and the other is that they require little or no chemical and/or mechanical pre-treatment of samples, which is very important in the field of cultural heritage²⁶⁻²⁸. Moreover, all of these techniques could complement each other to improve results and thanks to recent developments in spectroscopic imaging, it is now easier to extract more useful information in less time. One of the most valuable kinds of information provided by spectroscopic imaging is the display of chemical compound distribution^{16, 29}.

Taking into account the well known penetration capacity of pollutants via atmospheric depositions or infiltrations, this type of analysis could help to describe the penetration pattern of pollutants in a diversity of building materials. Above all, this kind of analysis may be necessary because the composition of the surface might not be representative of the material. That is, the surface is directly affected by external agents, such as rainwater, wind, etc, and the outmost layer can be washed out and pollutants removed from the surface as a result. Moreover, the initial phases of flaking might not be identified by surface analysis.

Despite the useful information it provides, cross-section analysis is not commonly used when evaluating the state of conservation of buildings materials affected by environmental stressors. In fact, this kind of analysis on buildings is usually related to architectural or industrial studies³⁰⁻³², but in the field of built heritage the number of studies is scarce^{6, 7, 33, 34}.

Therefore, the objective of this work was to evaluate the usefulness of studying cross-sections prepared from test drillings as a routine procedure, in order to characterise the

physicochemical damage suffered by building materials. For this purpose, some depth profiles obtained on real samples using a combination of spectroscopic imaging techniques were studied.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Sampling

Pollution levels affecting the area of metropolitan Bilbao (North of Spain) have decreased considerably over the last few years, but even now the consequences of environmental stressors impacting on building materials for decades are notable. For this reason, the pollutant content of different buildings located in the area has been studied in recent works^{5, 6, 35}. These studies have revealed marked impact of atmospheric pollution on buildings and by comparing the inner and outer surfaces of extracted samples, have shown the significant penetration capacity of the identified pollutants. Therefore, in order to evaluate the importance of cross-section analysis in assessing building materials, different buildings from the first half of twentieth century under restoration were selected for sampling. Samples of mortar, brick and concrete were collected using a drilling ring in dry mode so that salts would not dissolve during extraction. An 18 mm diameter drilling ring was used in order to obtain core samples at least 5 mm thick. However, when of a core as a whole piece was not possible due to the poor state of some materials (powdering) a chisel was used for sampling. The thickness of the samples varied but was never less than 5 mm (Figure 1). Table 1 summarizes the characteristics of the samples used in this work to illustrate the need for depth profiling in conservation studies.

Sample treatment

In order to improve focusing and therefore the spectroscopic images obtained, samples are usually polished prior to analysis. The polishing process was performed by the grinding & polishing machine Forcipol 1 (300 rpm fixed speed and 200 mm of wheel diameter) of Metkon without water so as to avoid the dissolution of soluble salts. As in the classical cross-section sample preparation, the samples were embedded in a resin to increase the resistance of the samples when it was necessary. In our case a cold method based on acrylic resin was chosen. This method involves a mixture of dry powder and liquid resin (Polirresin, bcn Quálites S.L.). After this, the samples were grinded using the silicon carbide grinding papers with the lower grits (1800/2000-grit) in order to avoid the material loss. However, the analyses made on these first samples revealed a lower soluble salt content than expected from visual inspection of the sampling area. Salts are weakly anchored to supporting materials and thus, the friction generated, both when using the drilling ring and when polishing, was apparently responsible for such salt loss. Consequently, despite the lower image quality, the cores and samples were fractured rather than grinded and polished in order to preserve the representativeness of the sample.

Instrumentation

Three different spectroscopic imaging techniques were selected.

Due to the irregularity of non-polished surfaces and to ensure an adequate focusing on each measurement, mappings were prepared using a combination of point-by-point μ -XRF measurements taken with Surfer 10.7.972 software. Elemental analysis was carried out using an ArtTax model micro X-ray Fluorescence spectrometer (μ -XRF) by Röntec

(currently Bruker). The measurement conditions for all spectra were a 50 kV voltage, 0.7 mA current, 500 s and 1.50 mm Tantalum collimator. The equipment has a Mo X-Ray tube and special Xflash detector (5mm²) and has a measuring head on a CCD camera that can be focused on the sample using a motorised XYZ positioning unit controlled by computer. Daily calibration of the equipment was carried out using a Röntec bronze reference standard.

In order to obtain a Raman chemical image a RenishawInVia confocal microRaman spectrometer with StreamLine™ Plus technology was used. This spectrometer is coupled to a DMLM Leica microscope (UK) focused through 20x lens (N PLAN EPI, 0.40 aperture, 1.1 mm working distance), and uses a 514 nm and a 785nm laser as excitation sources (the nominal laser power settings at the surface of the samples were 20 mW and 150 mW respectively), and a CCD detector (Peltier cooled). Wire 3.2 software (Renishaw, UK) was used for data collection. The microscope comprises a Prior Scientific motorised xyz stage system with a joystick and is equipped with a TV microcamera. Spectra were taken at a resolution of 1 cm⁻¹ in a static range at 790 cm⁻¹, 10 sg and 50% power. In order to improve spectra acquisition, point-by-point analyses were also carried out with a Renishaw RA 100 Raman spectrometer coupled to an fibre optic microprobe joined to a 20x lens (5 µm lateral resolution), at 785 nm excitation wavelength (using 100% laser power, the nominal laser power at the sample was 235 mW), and a Peltier cooled CCD detector. Data was obtained using Wire 3.2 software (Renishaw, Oxford, UK). The Raman microprobe is mounted on a tripod and coupled to a TV microcamera that can focus on areas of interest. The laser beam spot was focused on 10-200 µm and spectra were taken in the range 100-3250 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 2

cm⁻¹. E-visart and e-visarch dispersive Raman and FT-Raman spectral databases were used for the interpretation of some results^{36,37}.

Finally, the cross-sections were analysed under a scanning electron microscope in order to obtain the microscopic distribution and composition of the pollutant compounds affecting the samples. SEM-EDX analysis was used to acquire electron images and to determine elemental composition and was carried out using a Carl Zeiss NTS GmbH EVO®40 Scanning Electron Microscope coupled to Oxford Instruments X-Max Energy-Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy equipment. SEM images were obtained at high vacuum using a 30kV acceleration voltage and an 8-10 mm working distance. Different magnifications were used to take the images using a secondary electron detector. Elemental analysis was carried out using an 8.5 mm working distance, a 45° take-off angle and a 30kV acceleration voltage and an integration time of 100-200 s was used to improve the signal to noise ratio. Finally, the INCA Suit version 4.13 package was used to obtain the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All of the following results evidence the need for cross-section analysis in order to determine the depth and distribution of pollutants. Otherwise, conclusions obtained from surface analysis alone could be incomplete or erroneous as will be demonstrated below.

The Raman analysis on the surface of sample M1 (see Figure 2a) revealed hematite (α -Fe₂O₃, detected Raman bands at 612, 408, 292 (vs) and 224 cm⁻¹), quartz (SiO₂, identified Raman bands at 1157, 464 (vs), 396, 355, 265 and 202 cm⁻¹) and aluminosilicates (intense and broad bands at 1700-1100 cm⁻¹) as original compounds.

Calcite (CaCO_3 main Raman bands at 1086 (vs), 712, 280 and 157 cm^{-1}) was also identified but, due to its nature, it is difficult to determine whether it is an original or a degradation compound. In the blackened area analysis showed typical black crust composition: carbon with characteristic bands at 1600 and 1300 cm^{-1} and gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, identified by Raman bands at 1133, 1007 and 412 cm^{-1}). In addition, insoluble anhydrite in the rhombic structure (CaSO_4 , with main Raman band at 1025 cm^{-1}) was also identified. Therefore, according to surface analysis by Raman spectroscopy, the results obtained could be accounted for by the effect of atmospheric SO_2 on the façade.

On the other hand, the cross-section analysis of the same sample revealed the presence of calcite subefflorescences in the detached area, as can be seen in Figure 2b. The formation of these subefflorescences involves the dissolution of carbonates in the sample and reprecipitation as calcite. Considering the stability of natural calcite the presence of carbonates is probably a consequence of the carbonation of concrete due to CO_2 attack. In addition, the location of the subefflorescences suggests that the physical stress due to calcite formation within the pores was responsible for spalling. This finding would be impossible if only surface analysis were carried out, which would give incomplete results pointing only to a SO_2 attack.

Another mortar analysed was a rendering mortar (M2) composed of sand and cement. A visual examination of the sample revealed that this mortar does not have a black crust but does have a beige patina covering the whole surface. The μ -XRF image revealed that the patina was 1 mm thick and mainly composed of silicon. According to the Raman image of the patina area, the first $100 \mu\text{m}$ of the patina were composed of quartz

(SiO₂, main Raman band at 464 cm⁻¹) (Figure 3a-b). The identification of this layer indicated an advanced deterioration process, probably due to the action of acid rainwater, which may have dissolved most of the materials. Under the patina, and thanks to the cross-section analysis, diverse degradation compounds were identified at different depths, some of them not identified on the surface. In this way, gypsum, calcite and nitrocalcite (Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, detected Raman band at 1048 cm⁻¹) reached as much as 11mm depth, as can be seen in Figure 3c. Occasionally a very strong and broad Raman band at 1049 cm⁻¹ was also observed. The breadth of this band meant that the presence of another nitrate compound could not be ruled out. Therefore, cross-section analysis evidenced the presence of sulphates and nitrates and consequently, acid gases including SO₂ and NO_x must have had an impact. These sulphates and nitrates are formed when calcium carbonate from the original composition of the sample is attacked by the mentioned gases to form, usually, gypsum and nitrocalcite respectively. However, one cannot rule out the use of additives as the origin of the detected sulphates⁷. Moreover, these compounds were not identified on the surface, probably because they are soluble enough to be removed by rainwater and migrate to the interior through the pore net^{6, 38}. In any case, the described deterioration could not have been identified using surface analysis alone.

Coming back to the XRF analysis of the mortars (M1 and M2), mappings allowed elements not identified by Raman spectroscopy to be determined. For instance, chlorine and bromine were found in the interior of the sample (M1). These elements could not be identified in surface elemental analysis and chlorides and bromides cannot be detected by Raman spectroscopy due to their symmetry. Their major presence in the interior can

be explained as a consequence of the solubilisation of the respective salts on the surface by rain, as previously exposed in the case of nitrates. Moreover, the accumulation of elements such as sulphur, lead, zinc and chromium were also observed with a penetration capacity of around 3 mm inside the black crusted mortar.

Likewise, sulphur, bromine and chlorine were also identified as penetrating pollutants below the patina in sample M2. In this case, XRF images revealed the accumulation of nickel in the patina area, probably due to deposition of atmospheric particulate matter. It is worth highlighting that surface deposition can be distinguished from penetrating pollution by cross-section analysis, which allows us to determine the depth reached by pollutants.

Finally, the mortar sample (M2) broke during cross-section analysis. The SEM image revealed an important number of microscopic cracks in the interior of the mortar. Moreover, focusing on the crack area where the sample had broken, EDX analysis revealed sodium chloride deposits. These deposits were heterogeneously distributed and accumulated especially in the cracks (Figure 4). As such, the evidence suggests that this compound causes the mortar to crack from the pressure generated by the formation of salt crystals.

Carbon was also found showing the same behaviour as sodium chloride, accumulating on the surface and around the crack. The presence of this compound was probably due to soot washed out by penetrating/infiltration water. As in the case XRF images, sulphur was again related to Ca, probably forming as gypsum, which was identified penetrating up to 11 mm in some areas.

In the case of the brick core sample (B3), the surface was covered with a joint mortar, visibly carbonated by the action of CO₂. Firstly, thanks to Raman image analysis, the distribution of different original compounds such as quartz or aluminosilicates was observed. The photograph of the cross-section showed many subefflorescences at up to 2 mm depth. These were assigned to calcite by Raman spectroscopy imaging results (see Figure 5a). Due to the manufacturing process of bricks the presence of calcite can be generally related to two different processes: incorrect manufacture of the brick (a low kiln temperature that does not ensure proper vitrification of the surface) or a degradation process. The first option is unlikely, considering the distribution of the calcite. That is, when firing is incomplete, the major calcite crystals are usually found inside the materials, whereas in this case, the gradient of calcite crystals increases towards the outside. This trend was also observed in μ -XRF and SEM-EDX analyses. μ -XRF images of calcium revealed accumulation in approximately the first 4.5 mm in the areas close to the mortar but not on the rest of surfaces exposed to the environment (Figure 5b). So these results point to the dissolution and penetration of mortar components as the most probable calcite source. In order to clarify this point, SEM-EDX analysis was performed on a core showing the interface area between the mortar and the brick. According to the results, the calcium concentration pattern of the brick has a gradient that decreased with depth (Figure 5c). In addition, the high calcium and carbon concentration in the pore net of the brick suggested that calcite components, which precipitate under dry conditions (Figure 5d-e), had penetrated the pores. The precipitation of calcite in this form could cause cracks affecting the integrity of the brick. So, regarding the origin of calcium and carbon, taking into account the mortar found covering the brick surface, calcite in the mortar (originally or after carbonation of

components) may have partially dissolved and penetrated the brick to deposit in the interior. Bearing in mind these results, the use of this kind of mortar is not recommended, not only because of the dissolution and penetration of the components (forming cracks and increasing susceptibility to deterioration (higher porosity, greater surface area,...)), but also because, as shown in previous results, calcite can transform into more soluble salts, as in the case of nitrates, causing material to be lost.

Returning to the XRF imaging results of the brick, sulphur distribution was similar to that of calcium, suggesting gypsum formation, as can be seen in Figure 6a. This means that apart from carbonates, sulphates are also released from the mortar. With regard to the exposed surface, copper, zinc, lead and nickel were identified and probably constitute atmospheric particulate matter. In fact, many factories (such as metallurgy or chemical industries) are located near the sampling area and may be a source of deposition of these heavy metals. However, the contamination due to these metals was not only present on the surface. According to the μ -XRF maps (not included), zinc was the most penetrating metal, reaching up to 0.3-0.4 mm depth. In fact, some other metals usually attributed to atmospheric pollution were also identified in the brick sample. Until now, the presence of chrome and barium, for example, detected during surface analysis has generally been explained as deposition of atmospheric particles. However, the cross-section analysis showed a homogeneous distribution of the elements inside the sample (Figure 6-b). Therefore, chromium and barium were apparently part of the composition of the raw materials (maybe slag) used in brick manufacturing³⁹. So, it can be seen that cross-section analysis show that metals that have always been considered anthropogenic, may in fact originate from other sources.

Regarding the analyses performed on the concrete sample C4, an initial examination of the cross-section showed two different layers: The first (outer) 16 mm had a whiter colour that, according to μ -XRF image shown in Figure 6, had a different composition. For instance, the outer layer contained less calcium and potassium than the inner one. Furthermore, heavy metals such as tin and cadmium were identified at depths up to 4 mm. Taking into account the lower porosity of the concrete compared to the mortars, this is considered a significant degree of penetration. Moreover, the presence of a highly penetrating sulphur and lead was identified. In both cases, the pollutant penetrates a few millimetres into the second layer which seems to be more compact (Figure 6c-d). This penetration capacity of sulphur is quite profound, but the most remarkable result is the high concentration and penetration reached by the lead (up to 20 mm). These results are surprising if inorganic lead compounds are considered because they are often non soluble and hence, they have reduced mobility. However, this penetration could be explained if the diffusion of a lead based gas were considered. As such, one of the most likely possibilities is tetraethyl lead, which has been one of the combustion products of leaded fuels until recently^{40, 41}.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the use of the cross-section analysis using a combination of spectroscopic imaging techniques lead to the conclusion that this methodology allows researchers to obtain important and varied information about samples, more complete and exact than obtained by surface analysis alone. In fact, surface analysis usually leads to

incomplete or even incorrect conclusions. The most important information obtained from imaging analysis of cross-sections is the following:

- i) Differentiation of surface deposition from penetrating pollution.
- ii) Elemental and molecular compound distribution. Therefore, this information allows researchers to determine the original source of the compounds/elements found depending on the homogeneity observed.
- iii) The depth reached by the pollutants. This is related to material porosity and sometimes the physicochemical form of the pollutant may be suggested.
- iv) SEM-EDX images allowed surface and internal cracks to be detected, and the causes of these physical stresses to be identified as well.

In conclusion, cross-section analysis on test drillings, which is commonly used in other fields but not in built heritage, is essential as a routine analysis procedure to avoid incorrect and/or incomplete damage assessment of building materials. Moreover, knowledge of the composition of building materials allows proper safety measures to be established in restoration work, as this article and previous works demonstrate⁴ that certain façade materials should be treated as hazardous.

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Figure 1.- Examples of the measured samples. (a) The size of the drilling ring used was as smaller as possible in order to obtain a hole easy to be refilled. Core samples of cement (b) and brick (c) were obtained when possible. Materials with low integrity were sampled by a chisel (d). Samples were fractured for the analysis of the interior surface (e).

Figure 2.- (a) Image of the mortar sample M1 where a white crust is observed (b) Raman spectra taken on the surface of this sample.

Figure 3.- Composition for the mortar sample M2. (a) XRF image of silicon where one millimeter thickness of patina was analyzed. (b) Raman spectroscopy image of quartz for the first 400 μm of the patina where such compound was identified as the major compound in the first 100 μm. (c) Raman spectra at 11mm depth.

Figure 4.- (a) SEM image of the crack of sample M2 and (b) EDX maps for chlorine and (c) sodium which revealed the formation of NaCl deposits in the surface and in the capillary with the subsequent crack promotion.

Figure 5.- Composition for the brick sample B3. (a) Raman spectroscopy image of calcite reaching at least 2 mm depth. (b) XRF image for calcium in the brick where the highest concentration was found in the areas in contact with the carbonated joint mortar. (c) SEM-EDX map of calcium from the interface

area between the brick and the joint mortar. Zoom on the maps for (d) calcium and (e) carbon showing an accumulation of calcium carbonate in the capillaries.

Figure 6.- In the top, XRF images for (a) sulphur and (b)barium distributions in the brick sample B3, which allows the source of the elements found to be determined. In the bottom, XRF images of the concrete sample C4 for (c) lead and (d) sulphur which evidences a very penetrating pollution that reaches up to 20 mm depth.

Table 1.-Summary of the characteristics of the samples used in this work.

Code	Description
M1	Black crusted rendering mortar affected by spalling and collected in the first floor of a building suffering several floods
M2	Mortar with a beige patina of 1 mm belonging to a building affected by floods in the past
B3	Brick sample collected from a wall close to an industrial area (metallurgical, chemical,...) and affected by marine traffic
C4	Concrete sample belonging to a railing located three meters height in a building near to a road and a harbour

Figure 7.-“for TOC only”